

HUMAN VALUE IN THE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY MANIFESTATION

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Abstract

This article presents legal guarantees of human rights and freedoms, personal, political, economic rights of citizens, the role of citizens in the life of society, the conditions created for them in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords

Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, legal state, citizen, personal and Political Law, decision, article, democracy, equal rights

In the last 5 years in our country, within the framework of the action strategy, effective work has been carried out to increase the role of the Oliy Majlis in the system of state power, to solve important tasks related to the country's domestic and foreign policy, and to further expand the powers of parliamentary control over the activities of the executive branch. The development strategy of New Uzbekistan, put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, as a logical continuation of these reforms, included huge milestones for the next five years. In this important conceptual document, in order to ensure the integrity and continuity of reforms, the principle "From Action Strategy to Development Strategy" was put on the agenda as the main idea and main criterion. (T. Abbaskhanov. Journal of "Civil Society" on some issues of information analytical provision of parliamentary activity, 2022, issue 1, p. 29-30)

What are the tasks to be done in the next five years, that is, the country's development strategy? The direct answer to these questions is reflected in the three sources related to the activity of President Shavkat Mirmonovich Mirziyoyev, i.e. the book "Strategy of New Uzbekistan", the President's speech at the Inauguration ceremony, as well as the Decree "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026".

It is no exaggeration to say that the development strategy has become a real Uzbek program. Usually, according to the tradition of our people, before starting a

big work, many people are consulted. During the consultation process, ideas and suggestions are put forward. After heated discussions, a final decision is reached with the majority and the work is started. The popular nature of the development strategy can be seen from the fact that its project was discussed by the public through mass media and social networks. During the discussions, more than 17,000 suggestions were made by our compatriots, and it is a happy fact that most of them were used to improve the project. Proposals to use the discussion of the Development Strategy project, which is the program for the development of our country in the next five years, their reflection in the program document is evidence of the development of free civil society in our country. In this program document, developed on the basis of the implementation of the noble ideas "For the value of man", "The state is for man" formed on the basis of the principle "Man - society - state", the trends of socio-economic development in the near and medium term, and priority tasks in this regard are defined. It is recognized that special attention is paid to ensuring the integrity and continuity of the reforms based on the principle of "From the strategy of actions to the strategy of development" and serves the development of all areas, the place of Uzbekistan among the developed countries, and the fulfillment of the great wishes of our people to build a fair, free and prosperous society. Building a people-friendly state by increasing human dignity and further development of a free civil society is one of the main points of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026. If we take into account that in order to bring human value to higher levels, as in advanced democracies, it is the middle and small owners' stratum, their owning private property, as well as the result of this stratum's implementation of the ideology of liberalism, that the representatives of the middle stratum, where freedom is forming as an independent social stratum in Uzbekistan, have not yet risen to the level of active participation in political parties or public and non-governmental organizations and trade unions.

In the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan, important tasks aimed at the formation of a new image of the penal system aimed at effectively protecting the dignity and rights and freedoms of prisoners in Uzbekistan were defined. Convicts are also human beings first of all, that is why the humanitarian policy carried out by our state covers all categories of the population. Positive changes are also taking place in the attitude towards convicts, that is, those who have served and are serving their sentences. First of all, the primary goal in prisons is not to punish, but to educate prisoners. A lot of attention is paid to pardoning convicts who sincerely regret their crime, realize their mistakes and are committed to recovery, and give them a chance to start their lives anew. In particular, the fact

that 5352 persons were pardoned by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the past five years is a proof of our opinion. 1,816 of those pardoned are those who participated in the activities of banned organizations, 398 are women, 220 are foreign citizens, and 163 are elderly people over 60 years old. Another noteworthy aspect is that due to the increased practice of using alternative punishments unrelated to imprisonment instead of imprisonment in our country, 4 closed type colonies, number 19 in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, number 36 in the Navoi region, number 33 in the Kashkadarya region, 65 general order colonies in Tashkent region have been completed. Instead of the investigative detention center No. 1 in the city of Tashkent, a modern building that fully meets international standards was built and commissioned in Zangiota district. \ Rustam Turgunov.- Humanitarianism and democratic principles are the main criteria of our activity.- "Democratization and human rights" magazine 2022 - issue 37- page. In the last five years, 3 laws, 1 decree of the President, 6 decisions, 10 decisions and decrees of the Government, 15 departmental and interdepartmental regulatory legal documents were adopted in order to improve the system of punishment execution.

In particular, the implementation of the "Minimum Standards of Treatment of Prisoners" (Nelson Mandela Rules) adopted on the basis of the resolution of the UN General Assembly into our national legislation was an important event. In this way, it was ensured that the honor and dignity of the prisoners were not harmed and they were respected, and the use of torture and cruel punishments was prevented. (R. Tursunov - Humanity and democratic principles are the main criteria of our activity - "Democratization and human rights" magazine - 2022 issue 2, page 389)

On June 26, 2021, the decision of the Honorable President PQ-5163 "On additional measures to identify cases of torture and improve the system of their prevention" (Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan - June 2021) to observe the principle of humanity in the system of punishment activities of public groups to identify cases of torture and prevent them were launched. The public group was established under the Ombudsman, and they are required to regularly carry out monitoring visits to prevent torture in places where persons with limited freedom of movement are kept, to study the conditions in places where prisoners are kept, to identify cases of torture and to submit requests to the relevant state activities for their prompt elimination. tasks such as doing. According to the Law "On Additions to the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at improving the procedure for compensation of damages caused to victims of

torture" approved by the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the first article of Article 951 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Illegal sentencing, illegal prosecution, after the words "unlawful application of detention as a preventive measure or receiving a certificate of good behavior, illegal imposition of administrative punishment in the form of imprisonment" and "any torture and other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment and types of punishment" application" was filled with the words, and the rest of the text was left. Also, in the third paragraph of the second part of Article 1021, after the words "detention", the words "as well as the use of any torture and other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment and types of punishment" were specified. (Newsletter of the Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2022, No. 3, 218m.)

In the last five years, in order to ensure the transparency of the conditions of detention of prisoners and to prevent negative situations such as various irregularities, torture and insincere treatment of them, the prisons were equipped with 4 thousand modern video surveillance devices.

Article 12 of the Criminal-Executive Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is called "Ensuring freedom of conscience of prisoners". According to him, "Prisoners are guaranteed freedom of conscience. They have the right to practice any religion they want or not to practice any religion. At their request, priests of religious associations registered in the prescribed manner are invited to the presence of persons serving a sentence of imprisonment or deprivation of liberty. Prisoners are allowed to perform religious rituals, use things necessary for prayer and religious literature.

Today, there are 18,361 pieces of religious literature, including 717 Qurans, 16,937 books on Islam, 201 Bibles and 506 books on other religions, in the libraries of penal institutions. In our national legislation, there is no concept of dividing prisoners into religious, political or other categories. All persons serving a sentence shall be kept under the same conditions in accordance with the requirements of the criminal executive code and shall serve their sentence in orderly institutions determined by the court's verdict. In general, the rights of prisoners, regardless of their gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, belief, personality, and social status, are not allowed to be discriminated against, their dignity cannot be undermined, because our national legislation and international normative legal documents stipulate criminal responsibility for this. Placed. In our country, punishment for crime, its execution, and policy have also changed on the basis of humanitarian principles. Non-custodial punishments were introduced into the criminal law, and the Probation Service was established to enforce these types of

punishments. Some of the persons serving the sentence in penal institutions committed crimes intentionally and repeatedly, while some committed crimes unknowingly, as a result of carelessness or for other reasons. Penitentiary institutions help them to realize the consequences of their actions and to repent of their actions, to improve their morals. In the course of educational work in institutions, attention is paid to their finding their place in society after release. In the Development Strategy of Uzbekistan, to ensure the rights of convicts to work, to receive social security and other internationally recognized rights, to introduce effective methods of assisting their social adaptation and renewal into society after their release, to establish joint activities of state and community institutions in this direction, and to consistently improve the existing legislation in this regard implementation of the humane principle of sentencing and execution system, improvement of preventive mechanisms to prevent torture, implementation of effective practical mechanisms of punishment execution system, as well as modern information technologies, establishment of electronic document exchange with state bodies and other organizations important tasks aimed at forming a new image of the punishment execution system aimed at effective protection of public interests, including the dignity, rights and freedoms and interests of prisoners, were determined. It should be noted that improving the labor relations system, ensuring employment of the population, ensuring decent working conditions and preventing forced labor in the development strategy have gained priority in the development strategy and have been raised to the level of state policy. The following priority principles are the basis for achieving a qualitatively new level of systematic work in this area and, most importantly, positively affecting the interests of all sections of the population.

In particular:

- openness of state administration bodies;
- communication with the people;
- all-round support of civil authority institutions;
- evaluating any situation related to forced labor as an emergency;
- systematic provision and protection of the rights of citizens operating in foreign countries;
- introduction of international standards to the decent labor system;

The work carried out on the basis of these principles serves to fundamentally improve all areas, including the labor market and the system of labor relations.

Today, as a result of comprehensive reforms implemented in the sector, concrete results have been achieved in terms of ending forced labor. In particular,

on March 10, 2022, the "Cotton Campaign" international coalition officially announced the cancellation of the "cotton boycott" against Uzbekistan.

The cancellation of the global boycott imposed on Uzbek cotton by the "Cotton Campaign" international coalition was a vivid example of the effectiveness of large-scale reforms in our country. It should be noted that the cancellation of the boycott of Uzbek cotton served to create millions of new decent jobs in our country, primarily in the regions, to increase the level of employment of the population, opened new markets, and made it possible to implement new investment projects.

The achieved success is the result of large-scale and systematic reforms in the field of labor relations, which were carried out in the following directions:

- strengthening of legislation and organizational-legal base;
- implementation of international standards;
- agricultural reform;
- development of institutional foundations;
- conducting systematic monitoring and research;
- activation of cooperation with civil society and specialized international organizations; (The same work - page 5)

thus, from now on, work in the direction of combating forced labor will be systematically continued, relations with international organizations will be strengthened, new projects and measures will be implemented to ensure human dignity and rights and freedoms, and to create decent working conditions.

In particular, national legislation related to the field will be further improved based on international standards, issues of ratification of a number of conventions in the field of labor will be considered. In short, in the measures defined in each paragraph of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for the years 2022-2026, all efforts are made to glorify human dignity, will and honor, and tomorrow's prosperous lifestyle and the future of our country are reflected. The measures specified in each paragraph of the development strategy of our newly independent country for 2022-2026 will further protect the interests of the citizens of our country and create a basis for them to make a worthy contribution to the development of our country.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-158 dated September 11, 2023 "Uzbekistan 2030 "Strategy" was approved. According to it, the following reforms were set as a goal. They consist of:

1. To create suitable conditions for everyone to realize their potential;
2. Ensuring the well-being of the population through sustainable economic growth;

3. Conservation of water resources and environmental protection;
4. Ensuring the supremacy of law, organization of public administration in the service of the people;
5. It included reforms such as consistent continuation of the policy based on the principle of "safe and peaceful state".

"Uzbekistan 2030 Strategy" is aimed at building a free, prosperous, and powerful New Uzbekistan of our people, raising human dignity and raising a morally mature generation, ensuring justice and the rule of law, security and stability, and making the young generation legally mature. I believe that the teachers who are educating will do their best to fulfill their duties diligently.

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